

Conference Abstract

Challenges and Strategies in Implementing and Monitoring Long-Term Ecological Restoration Projects in Portugal

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Abstract

Ecosystem restoration is crucial for halting biodiversity loss and reversing environmental degradation, playing a key role in addressing the climate crisis and ensuring global human well-being and security. The long-term success and cost-effectiveness of restoration efforts depend on continuous monitoring and management.

Here, we explore the main challenges in ecological restoration project implementation, scientific monitoring, and present preliminary findings on changes in plant community composition and diversity. These changes are assessed in response to both short- and long-term climatic conditions, as well as the effects of passive and assisted restoration techniques in Portugal. The projects focus on three distinct contexts: the restoration of a coastal dune system, the rehabilitation of a limestone quarry, and the recovery of agroforestry systems in dryland regions.

The ecological restoration of the dunes in S. João da Caparica began in 2014. Scientific monitoring since then has demonstrated the successful establishment of vegetation and faunal communities, alongside positive geomorphological evolution. These results confirm that dune restoration is an effective strategy for protecting coastal ecosystems.

The restoration of a quarry site in Arrábida Natural Park started in 1983 and has been under continuous scientific monitoring. After 30 years, the restored vegetation has low similarity to the natural reference and shows a stabilization trend in some recovery indicators, primarily influenced by soil characteristics and the type of restoration intervention (plantations or hydroseeding). Our findings have helped evaluate recovery progress, identify limiting factors, and propose adaptive management strategies to enhance restoration outcomes.

Agroforestry systems of oak woodlands (montado) dominating in Portuguese drylands are in decline due to complex environmental pressures, including climate change and unsustainable land use. Over the past decades, several restoration projects have been implemented to enhance their resilience and adaptability to climate change conditions. Its scientific monitoring over the years has provided valuable insights into climate change impacts, guiding land management strategies and informing decision-making to combat desertification and improve the sustainability of these vital dryland agroforestry systems.

Keywords

Ecological restoration, Long-term monitoring, Biodiversity, Climate change, Arid Ecosystem,

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.